
A Critical Study on Strategic Management Research in Top Business Schools in India during last 5 Years

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Abstract

Strategic management is a subject added to business management area during 1960-1970 with an intention of supporting top level management of business organizations to suggest a method to fulfill the goals, purpose, and initiatives of the organization. This also includes the formulation and implementation of the objectives of the organization by means of optimum utilization of various resources and by analysing internal and external environment of the organization including its competitors. Number of strategic management models and frameworks are developed by many researchers and practitioners during last 50 years to which supports organizations to identify and face the challenges both internally and externally to the organizations by means of effective utilization of all possible resources in a systematic and smart manner to ensure winning in any situations. Various generic strategies at operational level, business level, and corporate level are identified/developed by many researchers and their effectiveness are tested by means of model development, empirical studies, and also through case analysis. Many institutions of business management are started strategic management division in their faculties and focussed on strategic management research. This paper focuses on the present status of strategic management research in some of top management research institutions in India including many Indian Institute of Managements. The contributions of research & publications of the strategic management divisions of these top business schools for the last 5 years are identified and analysed.

Keywords : *Strategic Management Research in India, Strategic management divisions, Indian business schools, Research publications.*

1. Introduction

Business Management as a field of study has many core subjects. In higher education level, Business management course include core subjects like Principles of management, Organizational behaviour, Micro & Macroeconomics, National & International business environment, Business law, Operations research, Business research methodologies, Production and Operation management, Marketing

management, Financial management & accounting, Human resource management, Information systems, Strategic management, Small business & entrepreneurship etc. Among them, Strategic management is a subject added to business management area during 1960-1970 and useful to the managers at the executive level to make right decisions at right time. This subject is developed with the intention of supporting top level management of business organizations to suggest a method to fulfill the goals, purpose, and initiatives of the organization. This also includes the formulation and implementation of the objectives of the organization by means of optimum utilization of various resources and by analysing internal and external environment of the organization including its competitors. Number of strategic management models and frameworks are developed by many researchers and practitioners during last 50 years to which supports organizations to identify and face the challenges both internally and externally to the organizations by means of effective utilization of all possible resources in a systematic and smart manner to ensure winning in any situations. Various generic strategies at the operational level, business level, and corporate level are identified/developed by many researchers and their effectiveness are tested by means of model development, empirical studies, and also through case analysis. Many institutions of business management are started strategic management division in their faculties and focussed on strategic management research. This paper focuses on the present status of strategic management research in some of top management research institutions in India including many Indian Institute of Managements'. The contributions of research & publications of the strategic management divisions of these top business schools for the last 5 years are identified and analysed.

2. Objectives and Scope :

The paper focus on finding the answer to the following questions:

- (1) What is the current status of strategic management research in India?
- (2) How many people are working and researching in Indian top management Institutions?
- (3) What is their current interest level in finding new models, analysing existing strategic management models used in research analysis, and studying organizational strategies through case studies?
- (4) What is the number of research paper publications in refereed journals during last five years from the different category of faculty members including Professors, Associate Professors, and Assistant professors respectively?

3. Methodology :

The study is based on collecting the research publication data of various top business schools of India as published by NIRF Ranking of Govt. of India. The data are collected during the first week of April 2018 from the respective websites of the management institutions as well as using Google scholar search facility for 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 separately using Custom range search facility of Google scholar website - <https://scholar.google.co.in/>. Care is taken to avoid mix of data of different authors of same name. Publication data of four years three months is effectively collected for study and comparison. Five years research index is calculated by adding journal publications for all five years and dividing the sum by five. The Five years Research Index is only representative and measures the five years research productivity of individual faculty. The average Research index for 5 years for the entire department is also calculated for comparison.

4. Strategic Management Research :

4.1 Strategic Management Research in India :

In India, Strategic Management Research has its root from Vedic period placed between 2500 and 600 B.C.E. This is the age of the assimilation and culmination of the great Vedas, Aranyakas, and Upanishads which have influenced Indian thought process since then [1]. Further, during the Epic Period, placed between 600 B.C.E. to 200 C.E. the great epics of Mahabharata and Ramayana were written and the early development of Buddhism, Jainism, Shaivism and Vaishnavism took place simultaneously. Bhagavad-Gita, which is a part of Mahabharata considered as one of the three most

authoritative texts of Indian philosophical literature. Further, during the Sutra Period, dated approximately the early centuries of the Christian era, short enigmatic aphorisms named Sutras were written as treatises to the earlier schools of philosophical thoughts, in systematic and orderly forms. During the 17th century, called the Scholastic Period, commentaries on sutras were written and further commentaries on commentaries were also written by many philosophers, including Shankaracharya, Sridhara, Ramanujacharya, Madhvacharya, Vachaspati, Kumarlila, Udayana, Bhaskara, Jayanta, Vijnabhikshu, and Raghunatha. Along with commenting on the ancient systems, some of these philosophers have developed their own systems like Shankaracharya's Advaita, Ramanujacharya's Vihsishtadvaita and Madhvacharya's Dvaita systems [2]. All these literature have many concepts of strategic management to ensure winning in organizational objectives and winning an accepted task.

But the systematic and orderly recording of Strategy in business literature is a relatively newer term and is still evolving. In the 1960s the focus was on long range planning, in 1970s on portfolio approach, in 1980s on competitive strategy and in 1990s on core competencies and resource based view of the firm. During the year 2000 to 2010 a type of monopoly strategy called blue ocean strategy is discussed a lot and after 2010, due to enhanced focus on the sustainable environment, green ocean strategy got importance [3-10]. Presently, the Top business schools like IIMs, IITs, some of University Departments, and many private business schools have separate strategic management groups which are involved in theoretical, conceptual, empirical, observational, and case study based research in various Strategy aspects and publishing them in Journals, Conference proceedings, and books. Table 1 lists the Faculty Strength of Strategic Management Divisions in Top Management Institutions in India.

Table 1 : Faculty Strength of Strategic Management Divisions in Top Management Institutions

S. N	Management Schools	Assistant Professors	Associate Professors	Professors	Total
1	IIM Ahmadabad	02	01	02	05
2	IIM Bangalore	01	01	09	11
3	IIM Calcutta	03	02	02	07
4	IIM Indore	04	03	03	10
5	IIM Kozhikode	05	03	02	10
6	IIM Lucknow	02	03	03	08
7	Dept. of Management, IIT – New Delhi	01	0	01	02
8	XLRI – Jamshedpur	07	03	0	10
9	NITIE – Mumbai	0	02	0	02
10	MDI, Gurgaon	04	0	02	06
11	IIM, Tiruchirappalli	02	02	0	04
12	IMT, Ghaziabad	0	02	0	02
13	Institute of Rural Management, Anand	01	01	01	03
14	IMI, New Delhi	0	01	05	06
15	IIFT, New Delhi	0	03	02	05
16	ISB, Hyderabad	05	0	01	06

5. Contribution of Top Business Schools during last 5 Years (2014-2018) :

Top business schools are supposed to contribute to different areas of business management by doing research and development activities along with promoting academic knowledge to the students through adding those subjects both UG and PG courses. Many business schools in India have separate

strategic management departments with faculty members in different cadres and Masters and Research programmes. In this work, we conducted a web-based research to study the contribution of top business schools during last 5 years by studying the strategic management divisions availability, the publications of these divisions faculty members during last 5 years starting from 2013 to 2018 using their institutional websites and the publication data available in the personal website/institutional website of the faculty members and corresponding check in Google Scholar search data year wise. In our study, we have collected the publication data of 16 top business schools which have Strategic management divisions in India with two to eleven faculty members.

5.1 IIM- Ahmedabad :

The strategic management division of IIM Ahmedabad is a part of Business Policy department and is initiated to convey the concept of strategy and its usefulness by exposing students to a variety of organizational situations. It also focus on Firm / environment; Strategies and Resources; Strategies and Values; Business Ethics; Industry Structure Analysis; Evaluation of Corporate Strategy; Strategies for Growth and Diversification; Process of Strategic Planning; Stages of Corporate Development; Strategy Implementation through Structure, Values and Ideologies; McKinsey's Framework; Acquisition of Resources and Competence; Management of organizational Change [11]. As per the record, there are five faculty members with two professors, one associate professor and two assistant professors. The journal publications of the strategy group of IIM Ahmedabad is counted using Google scholar annual search facility and is listed in Table 2.

Table 2 : Strategy Group : IIM-Ahmedabad (under Business Policy)

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	5 years Total	Index
1	Amit Karna Associate Professor	01	02	05	01	-	09	1.08
2	Ajeet N Mathur Professor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
3	Chitra Singla Assistant Professor	01	0	0	01	0	02	0.4
4	Anish Sugathan Assistant Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
5	Sunil Maheshwari Professor	-	04	01	01	-	05	1.0
Average Research index for 5 years								0.54

5.2 IIM- Bangalore :

The Strategy Area of IIM Bangalore covers the entire spectrum of problems that affect the current globalized businesses. Apart from the core area of strategic management, these areas include international business, strategic alliances, new product development, and the management of technology and innovation, among others. The Area offers specialization in the field of Strategy for the doctoral-level FPM of the Institute. Other Area activities include case writing by faculty members, sponsored research and consulting. Themes of current business and research interests form the basis for a number of Executive Education Programmes that the Area members offer directly or in collaboration with faculty members from other Areas. Faculty members of the Strategy Area have also been publishing influential academic papers in international journals such as Strategic Management Journal, Organization Science, Management Science, Academy of Management Journal, Academy of Management Review, Administrative Science Quarterly, Journal of International Business Studies, Harvard Business Review, and Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization. Area members are on the boards of several companies and also serve on national committees dealing with strategic and policy issues [12]. As per the record, there are eleven faculty members with nine

professors, one associate professor and one assistant professor. The journal publications of the strategy group of IIM Bangalore is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 3.

Table 3 : Strategy Group : IIM-Bangalore

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	5 years Total	Average Index
1	Pranav Garg Assistant Professor	0	0	0	01	0	01	0.2
2	P D Jose Professor	0	0	03	0	0	03	0.6
3	Rishiksha T Krishnan Professor	01	01	-	01	0	03	0.6
4	Rejie George Pallathitta Professor	01	02	02	03	0	08	1.6
5	Murali Patibandla Professor	01	0	03	0	0	04	0.8
6	Ganesh N Prabhu Professor	02	0	0	0	0	02	0.4
7	S Raghunath Professor	0	0	0	01	0	01	0.2
8	J Ramachandran Professor	0	02	0	01	0	03	0.6
9	Deepak Kumar Sinha Professor	0	0	0	0	0	00	0.0
10	R Srinivasan Professor	02	0	0	01	0	03	0.6
11	Sai Yayavaram Associate Professor	0	01	0	0	0	01	0.2
Average Research index for 5 years								0.53

5.3 IIM- Calcutta :

The strategic management group of IIM Calcutta is interested in understanding the roots of differential firm performance and the dynamics of choice and change for enterprises. The eclectic research and teaching interests of the group faculty and doctoral students cover diverse areas including corporate strategy, international business, business strategy, entrepreneurship, management of public sector enterprises, organization theory, sustainability, strategy-as-practice, and strategy execution. Members of the Strategic Management Group engage closely with the world of practice through consulting assignments and executive education [13]. As per the record, there are seven faculty members with two professors, two associate professor, and three assistant professors. The journal publications of the strategy group of IIM Calcutta is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 4.

Table 4 : Strategy Group : IIM-Calcutta

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Anirvan Pant Associate Professor	0	0	0	02	0	02	0.4
2	Biswatosh Saha	0	0	02	01	01	04	0.8

	Professor							
3	Kaushik Roy Assistant Professor	0	01	02	01	0	04	0.8
4	Palash Deb Associate Professor	01	0	0	03	0	04	0.8
5	Ramya Tarakad Venkateswaran Assistant Professor	0	0	01	0	0	01	0.2
6	Saptarshi Purkayastha Assistant Professor	0	01	02	04	0	07	1.4
7	Sougata Ray Professor	0	06	01	02	01	10	2.0
	Average Research index for 5 years							0.914

5.4. IIM – Indore :

As per the record, the strategic Management group of IIM Indore consists of ten faculty members with three professors, three associate professor and four assistant professors [14]. The journal publications of the strategy group is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 5.

Table 5 : Strategy Group : IIM-Indore

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Shubhabrata Basu Associate Professor	03	01	01	0	0	05	1.0
2	Sasanka Sekhar Chanda Assistant Professor	0	02	01	01	0	04	0.8
3	Swapnil Garg Associate Professor	0	0	01	01	0	02	0.4
4	Srinivas Gunta Assistant Professor	01	01	0	0	0	02	0.4
5	Manish Popli Assistant Professor	01	0	01	02	0	04	0.8
6	Prashant Salwan Associate Professor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	D. L. Sunder Professor	01	0	0	0	0	01	0.2
8	Koushik Dutta Professor	0	02	01	0	0	03	0.6
9	Kamal Sharma Assistant Professor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
10	Rishiksha T Krishnan Professor	01	01	0	01	0	03	0.6
								0.48

5.5. IIM – Kozhikode :

Strategic Management area of IIM Kozhikode consists of ten faculty members having doctorates from leading business schools. Almost all the area members have valuable experience of working in the responsible managerial positions in leading organisations. The faculty members have experience in teaching in leading business schools in India, USA, UK,

Europe and the Middle East. The area offers a number of elective courses for the Post Graduate Programme namely Entrepreneurship and New Ventures, Economics of Strategy, Strategy Implementation, Corporate Governance, Strategic Analysis of Joint Ventures and Alliances, Mergers Acquisitions and Corporate Growth, Strategic Flexibility and Resource Leverage in Organizations, Business Models for the 21st Century and Strategic Analytics. The research output produced by the faculty members in the last couple of years has been significant. The faculty members have published in leading academic journals and presented papers during major conferences of Academy of Management, Strategic Management Society, British Academy of Management and Academy of International Business. Broadly the faculty members conduct research in areas like strategic planning, business-level strategy, strategy implementation, entrepreneurship, international business, diversification, industrial clusters, capabilities, social networks, internationalisation of emerging market firms, renewable energy, policy issues in clusters, China and its energy policy, leveraging resources, business model innovation and strategic renewal of organizations [15]. The journal publications of the strategy group of IIM Kozhikode is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 6.

Table 6 : Strategy Group : IIM-Kozhikode

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total (N)	Index I=N/5
1	P. Rameshan Professor	0	0	0	2	0	02	0.4
2	M.K. Nandakumar Associate Professor	0	0	0	01	01	02	0.4
3	Ramesh Srinivas Upadhyayula Associate Professor	01	02	0	01	0	04	0.8
4	Sumit Mitra Professor	0	01	01	0	0	02	0.4
5	Suram Balasubrahmanyam Assistant Professor	01	0	0	01	0	02	0.4
6	Deepak Dhayanithy Assistant Professor	0	0	01	02	01	04	0.8
7	S.Subramanian Associate Professor	0	0	02	01	0	03	0.6
8	Anubha Shekhar Sinha Assistant Professor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
9	Dhirendra Mani Shukla Assistant Professor	0	0	02	0	01	03	0.6
10	Venkataraman S Assistant Professor	0	0	0	01	0	01	0.2

5.6. IIM - Lucknow

Strategic Management Group strives to become a knowledge storehouse for Indian organisational entities by specializing in top management functions and needs in the area of global competitiveness through knowledge creation and dissemination. SMG would accomplish this through new products/services of futuristic nature integrating on multiple knowledge platforms like business

planning, industry-structural dynamics, core competence, and entrepreneurship. The Group is engaged in PGP teaching in the following courses: Strategic Management, Competitive Strategies as compulsory courses; Management of Change, New Venture Planning, International Strategic Management, Mergers & Acquisitions and Management of Control Systems as electives. The strategic management division in IIM Lucknow consists of eight faculty members with three professors, three associate professor and two assistant professors [16]. The journal publications of the strategy group of IIM Lucknow is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 7.

Table 7 : Strategy Group : IIM-Lucknow

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Amita Mital Professor	-	01	-	01	01	03	0.6
2	Anadi Pande Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
3	Ashutosh Kumar Sinha Associate Professor	-	-	-	01	-	01	0.2
4	Krishna Chandra Balodi Associate Professor	02	01	01	-	-	04	0.8
5	Kshitij Awasthi Assistant Professor	-	-	01	-	-	01	0.2
6	Neeraj Dwivedi Professor	01	01	-	01	-	03	0.6
7	Rupanwita Dash Assistant Professor	-	-	-	01	-	01	0.2
8	Sabyasachi Sinha Associate Professor	-	01	02	01	-	04	0.8

5.7. Dept. of Management, IIT – New Delhi :

The strategic management division of Dept. Of Management, IIT, New Delhi consists of two faculty members with one professor, and one assistant professor [17]. The journal publications of the group is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 8.

Table 8 : Strategic Management Division, Dept. Of Management, IIT, Delhi

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Prof. Sushil Professor	4	5	4	5	2	20	4.0
2	Sanjay Dhir Assistant Professor	2	2	4	3	-	11	2.02

5.8. XLRI – Jamshedpur :

The strategic management division in XLRI Jamshedpur consists of ten faculty members with three associate professors and seven assistant professors [18]. The journal publications of the strategy group of XLRI Jamshedpur is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 9.

Table 9 : Strategic Management Division, XLRI

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Apalak Khatua Assistant Professor	-	01	01	01	-	03	0.6
2	Atul Arun Pathak Assistant Professor	01	06	03	03	-	13	2.6
3	Indrajit Mukherjee Assistant Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
4	Kalyan Bhaskar Assistant Professor	-	-	01	-	-	01	0.2
5	Manoj T Thomas Associate Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
6	Munish Thakur Assistant Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
7	Rajeev Sharma Associate Professor	-	03	-	-	-	03	0.6
8	Saroj Kumar Pani Assistant Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
9	Saurabh Kaushik Pandya Assistant Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
10	Tata L Raghu Ram Associated Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2

5.9 NITIE – Mumbai :

The strategic management division of NITIE – Mumbai consists of two associate professors [19]. The journal publications of the individuals is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 10.

Table 10 : Strategic Management Division, NITIE, Mumbai

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Som Sekhar Bhattacharyya Associate Professor	04	02	-	05	01	12	2.4
2	Utpal Chattopadhyay Associate Professor	01	02	02	01	01	07	1.4

5.10. MDI, Gurgaon :

The Strategic Management Area Faculty of MDI, Gurgaon specializes in strategic analysis and competitive analysis of firms in framing global and innovative strategies. The courses deal with entrepreneurship, cross cultural management, joint ventures and international business and merger and acquisitions. There are six faculty members in Strategic Management Division of MDI with two professors and four assistant professors [20]. The journal publications of the individual faculty

member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 11.

Table 11 : Strategic Management Division, MDI, Gurgaon

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Meeta Dasgupta Assistant Professor	01	01	-	-	-	02	0.4
2	Rajesh K Pillania Professor	-	01	-	-	-	1	0.2
3	Ankur Roy Assistant Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
4	Veeresh Sharma Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
5	Shiv S Tripathi Assistant Professor	01	-	01	-	-	2	0.4
6	Arun Kumar Tripathy Assistant Professor,	-	-	-	-	-	0	0

5. 11. IIM, Tiruchirappalli :

The strategic management division of IIM Tiruchirappalli consists of four faculty members with two associate professors and two assistant professors [21]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 12.

Table 12 : Strategic Management Division, IIM, Tiruchirappalli

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Karthik Dhandapani Associate Professor	-	02	-	01	-	03	0.6
2	Manikandan.K.S Assistant Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
3	Mukundhan K.V. Assistant Professor	-	-	01	-	-	01	0.2
4	Sankalp Pratap Associate Professor	01	-	01	01	01	04	0.8

5.12. IMT, Ghaziabad :

The strategic management division of IMT Ghaziabad consists of two associate professors [22]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 13.

Table 13 : Strategic Management Division, IMT, Ghaziabad

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Rakesh Gupta Associate Professor	02	01	-	01	01	05	1.0
2	Shalini Rahul Tiwari Associate Professor	02	02			01	05	1.0

5.13. Institute of Rural Management, Anand :

The strategic management group of Institute of Rural Management Anand, consists of three faculty members one professor, one associate professor, and an assistant professor [23]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 14.

Table 14 : Strategic Management Division, Institute of Rural Management, Anand

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Madhavi Mehta Professor	01	-	-	-	-	01	0.2
2	Pratik Modi Associate Professor	-	02	-	02	-	04	0.8
3	Satyendra Pande Assistant Professor	03	02	02	04	01	12	2.04

5.14. IMI, New Delhi :

The strategic management group of IMI New Delhi consists of six faculty members with five professors, and one associate professor [24]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 15.

Table 15 : Strategic Management Division, IMI, New Delhi

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Ashutosh Khanna Associate Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
2	G.K. Kapoor Professor	-	-	-	01	-	01	0.2
3	G.K. Agarwal Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
4	Parthasarathi Banerjee Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
5	Sonu Goyal Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
6	Vijay Vancheswar Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0

5.15. IIFT, New Delhi :

The strategic management group of IIFT, New Delhi consists of five faculty members including two professors, and three associate professors [25]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 16.

Table 16 : Strategic Management Division, IIFT, New Delhi

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	K. Rangarajan Professor	01	-	-	01	01	03	0.6
2	Rohit Mehtani Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
3	M.Venkatesan Associate Professor	-	-	02	-	01	03	0.6

4	Pooja Lakhanpal Associate Professor	-	-	-	-	-	0	0.0
5	Sweta Srivastava Malla Associate Professor	-	-	-	02	-	02	0.1

5.16. ISB, Hyderabad :

The top private business management school which offers one year Post graduate programme for experienced business executives in association with many foreign universities, the ISB, Hyderabad consists of six faculty members including one professor, and remaining five assistant professors [26]. The journal publications of the individual faculty member is counted using Google scholar annual search facility for last 5 years and is listed in Table 17.

Table 17 : Strategic Management Division, ISB, Hyderabad

S. No	Name of the Faculty & Designation	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	5 years Total	Index
1	Awate, Snehal Assistant Professor,	-	01		03	01	05	1.0
2	Chauradia, Amit Jain Assistant Professor	-	-	-	01	-	01	0.2
3	Damaraju, Naga Lakshmi Assistant Professor	-	01	-	02	-	03	0.6
4	Dixit, Jaya Assistant Professor	-	01	-	-	-	01	0.2
5	Ghosh, Anindya Assistant Professor	01	01	01	01	-	04	0.8
6	Harbir Singh Professor	-	03	-	02	-	05	1.0

6. Observations & Discussions :

The number of faculty members in strategic management division in each business school is summarized in table 18 along with the number of papers published during recent last 5 years and the average number of papers per year. The number of faculty members, their cadre in strategic management divisions of identified top business schools in India is used to calculate total faculty weightage by considering the following postulates :

- (1) One professor is equal to $8/6=1.33$ associate professors in terms of research and publication responsibilities.
- (2) One professor is equal to $8/4=2$ assistant professors in terms of research and publication responsibilities.
- (3) One associate professor is equal to $6/4=1.5$ assistant professors in terms of research and publication responsibilities.
- (4) If an assistant professor publishes 1 journal paper, an associate professor has to publish 1.5 paper and a professor has to publish 2 papers theoretically (1:1.5:2).

The above postulates are developed using UGC rule related to the permission to guide the maximum number of Ph.D. candidates at a given time. Accordingly, a professor can guide 8 Ph.D. candidates, an associate professor can guide 6 Ph.D. students, and an assistant professor can guide 4 Ph.D. candidate at a given time [27].

Thus in terms research and publication responsibility P:AsP:AP=8:6:4. That means if a person in Assistant professor cadre publishes 2 papers per year, a person in Associate professor cadre has to publish 3 papers per year and a person in Professor cadre has to publish 4 papers per year. Using the above analogy we have calculated the faculty weightage in each institute based on an available

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number of Strategic management faculty in each cadre and listed in table 19. Based on the faculty research weightage, the performance ranking of the strategic divisions of these business schools is determined and is also listed in table 19.

Table 18 : Faculty Strength of Strategic Management Divisions in Top Management Institutions

S. N	Management Schools	Total No. of Faculty	No. of Papers Published during last 5 years (till March 2018)	Average papers per year	Weighted Average papers per year
1	IIM Ahmadabad	05	17	3.4	0.68
2	IIM Bangalore	11	29	5.8	0.53
3	IIM Calcutta	07	32	6.4	0.91
4	IIM Indore	10	24	4.8	0.48
5	IIM Kozhikode	10	23	4.6	0.46
6	IIM Lucknow	08	17	3.4	0.425
7	Dept. of Management, IIT – New Delhi	02	31	6.2	3.10
8	XLRI – Jamshedpur	10	24	4.8	0.48
9	NITIE – Mumbai	02	19	3.8	1.90
10	MDI, Gurgaon	06	05	1.0	0.17
11	IIM, Tiruchirappalli	04	09	1.8	0.45
12	IMT, Ghaziabad	02	10	2.0	1.00
13	Institute of Rural Management, Anand	03	17	3.4	1.13
14	IMI, New Delhi	06	01	0.2	0.03
15	IIFT, New Delhi	05	08	1.6	0.32
16	ISB, Hyderabad	06	19	3.8	0.63

Table 19 : Faculty Strength of Strategic Management Divisions in Top Management Institutions

S. N	Management Schools	Total Faculty weightage	No. of Papers Published during last 5 years	Faculty Research weightage Index	Performance Ranking
1	IIM Ahmadabad	07.5	17	2.27	7
2	IIM Bangalore	20.5	29	1.41	12
3	IIM Calcutta	10.0	32	3.20	5
4	IIM Indore	14.5	24	1.66	11
5	IIM Kozhikode	13.5	23	1.70	10
6	IIM Lucknow	12.5	17	1.36	13
7	Dept. of Management, IIT – New Delhi	03.0	31	10.33	1
8	XLRI – Jamshedpur	11.5	24	2.09	8
9	NITIE – Mumbai	03.0	19	6.33	2
10	MDI, Gurgaon	08.0	05	0.63	15
11	IIM, Tiruchirappalli	05.0	09	1.8	9
12	IMT, Ghaziabad	03.0	10	3.33	4
13	Institute of Rural Management, Anand	04.5	17	3.77	3
14	IMI, New Delhi	11.5	01	0.087	16
15	IIFT, New Delhi	08.5	08	0.94	14

16	ISB, Hyderabad	07.0	19	2.71	6
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While studying above table 19, it is observed that :

- (1) The number of faculty members is varying institute to institute and is very small percentage compared to the overall number of faculty members in the institutes.
- (2) Several Top management institutes do not have faculties in professor cadre.
- (3) Many strategic management professors in top business schools are showing very less interest in research and publications compared to lower cadre faculty members.
- (4) The research and publication in strategic management area in top Indian institutions are not given priority.
- (5) The young faculty members in these institutions are also not given priority to research and publication.
- (6) In many cases, faculty members of the different cadres have not published even one paper per year.
- (7) In many cases it is observed that a faculty once reaches professor cadre, loses interest and commitment in research and publications due to the fact that there is no further promotion or demotion until their retirement due to no further evaluation of their performance.
- (8) It is also observed that faculty members including professors in strategic management do not have required number of Ph.D. scholars researching under their guidance. This also may be an added reason of decreased number of research publication.
- (9) Based on faculty research weightage index and performance ranking it is found that except one or two institutions, all other institutions are not giving importance to research and publications. Dept. of Management, IIT – New Delhi could able to maintain faculty research weightage index more than 10. The strategic management division of NITIE – Mumbai could able to maintain faculty research weightage index more than 5. In all other cases, the faculty research weightage index is very low and in such cases the institutions have to redefine their objectives and support to increase their research output by framing policies.

7. Conclusions :

During last sixty years after industrialization and globalization, strategic management concepts, theories, and models are gained importance. Strategic management research has evolved in five stages including (1) strategic financial planning, (2) Long range planning to ensure success, (3) Strategic planning of organization expansion, (4) Strategic Complex Static systems Planning & Management, and (5) Strategic complex dynamic systems planning & management. Many theories were developed to identify and implement right strategy at right time in order to organizational and individual success. Research in strategic analysis using various tools, techniques, and frameworks [33-48] also made decision process systematic and reliable. The paper emphasized the importance of research and publication in strategic management division which is one of the important areas of business management and presents the current scenario of research and publication in top Indian Business schools by studying recent five years journal publications in the area. It is observed that the contribution of faculty members in various cadres is not encouraging especially at professor cadre.

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